

Spectrophotometric Determination of Resorcinol

R. T. SANE*, B. D. BAMANE and J. G. MHALAS

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

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A simple spectrophotometric method of estimation of resorcinol is reported. Resorcinol forms a pink to violet-red colour with pyrocatechol and *l*-noradrenaline bitartrate in alkaline medium. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.8-8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of resorcinol for both the reagents. Ingredients like cetrimide, iodochlorohydroxyquinoline and bases like lanolin, kaolin, white paraffin etc. do not interfere.

RESORCINOL is formulated in pharmaceutical preparations in the form of ointments, lotions and creams for external application. Literature reveals many colorimetric¹⁻⁴, titrimetric^{5,6} and chromatographic⁷⁻⁹ methods for its estimation. The official method involves the iodometric titration¹⁰.

The present method is based on the observation of Eegriwe that if a dilute aqueous solution of resorcinol is treated with solid pyrocatechol and dilute sodium hydroxide, a transient blue-green colour appears and then gradually a pink to violet-red colour develops on the surface of the solution, slowly progressing downward and increasing in intensity¹¹. The production of the red colour is characteristic of resorcinol. The chemistry of the reaction is not known. This paper reports the results of the colour reaction with a view to developing it into a suitable spectrophotometric method for resorcinol.

Experimental

Apparatus: Spectra and absorbance measurements were made with a Beckmann, Model 26, double beam spectrophotometer; matched silica cells with a 1 cm optical path were used.

Reagents: Distilled water was deionized by passage through an ion exchange monobed prepared by mixing Amberlite IR-120 cation exchange resin (H^+ form) and Dowex 1-X8 anion exchange resin (OH^- form) together. The deionised water was collected and stored in a borosilicate glass carboy with minimal exposure to the atmosphere. The water had pH of 7.0, specific conductance of 4.0×10^{-7} ohm⁻¹, and was used for preparing all solutions.

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. 0.2 g of pyrocatechol was dissolved and the solution made upto 100 ml with deionised water to give a 0.2% solution. This solution should be freshly prepared. 1.38 g of AR potassium carbonate was dissolved and made upto 100 ml with deionised water to give a 0.1 M solution. 0.7 g of *l*-noradrenaline bitartrate was dissolved and made upto 100 ml

with deionised water to give a 0.7% solution. 10 mg of resorcinol was weighed accurately and dissolved in deionised water and made upto 100 ml to give a 0.1 mg/ml solution of resorcinol which was used as the standard. The other chemicals used were methanol, ethanol, *isopropanol* and *n*-*propanol*.

Analytical procedure :

To a 25 ml volumetric flask containing standard solution of resorcinol (20 μg to 200 μg resorcinol) were added 5 ml *isopropanol*, 0.5 ml 0.1 M potassium carbonate solution and 0.5 ml pyrocatechol reagent. The solution was mixed and diluted to 25 ml with deionised water. The absorbance of the pink to violet-red colour was measured at 558 nm after 20 min against the reagent blank. A similar procedure was followed by taking 0.5 ml of *l*-noradrenaline bitartrate as a reagent instead of pyrocatechol.

Results and Discussion

Pyrocatechol, which finds extensive application as an analytical reagent, has been widely used in the determination of many metals. Very few applications of pyrocatechol as a reagent in the determination of alkaloids¹², pharmaceuticals¹³ are reported. We have tested five *o*-dihydroxybenzene derivatives, viz., *l*-adrenaline bitartrate, *dl*-isoprenaline sulphate, methyl dopa, pyrocatechol and *l*-noradrenaline bitartrate as reagents for resorcinol but only the last two produced satisfactory results.

Beer's law and sensitivity : The graph of resorcinol concentration against the absorbance values was plotted. The graph obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.8-8.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of resorcinol. The colour reaction had a molar absorptivity of 1.69×10^4 using pyrocatechol and 1.41×10^4 using *l*-noradrenaline bitartrate as the reagent.

Effect of miscible solvents : The reaction was carried out in aqueous and in different organic solvent media. The solvents used were methanol, ethanol, *isopropanol* and *n*-*propanol*. The colour developed in 20-30% *isopropanol* was stable for nearly 1 hr as compared to 15 min in aqueous

medium. The colour intensity was also maximum in 20-30% isopropanol. Hence, 5 ml of isopropanol were used throughout the experiment.

Solvent extraction study :

The complex in aqueous medium was not extractable by chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, petroleum ether, butyl acetate, benzene or toluene.

Applications to pharmaceutical preparations :

Sample preparation :

Ointment and lotion : The amount of lotion or ointment corresponding to 100 mg of resorcinol was weighed in a beaker, 30 ml of water was added and heated on water bath at 60-70° for 15 min. The contents cooled, filtered and washed thoroughly and made upto 100 ml. 10 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml as the working sample.

Cream : In case of bismuth-resorcinate compounds, 2 ml of 1 N hydrochloric acid was added to break the complex and then the procedure as above

TABLE 1

Product	Resorcinol present (%)	Resorcinol found(%)		Resorcinol found by official method(%)
		1*	2*	
Ointment	1.75	1.72	1.70	1.70
Cream	3.0	3.03	3.01	3.05
Lotion	3.0	3.0	2.99	3.02

* With pyrocatechol reagent.

* With l-noradrenaline bitartrate reagent.

Conclusion :

The proposed method is simple, fast and accurate. The results obtained are reproducible and compare satisfactorily with those obtained by the official method. Commonly used bases in creams, lotions and ointments like lanolin, kaolin, white paraffin base, etc. produce no difficulty in estimation. Other commonly formulated ingredients like cetrimide, boric acid, iodochlorohydroxyquinoline, etc. do not interfere.

TABLE 2

Product	Standard deviation at different levels		Coefficient of variation at different levels	
	1*	2*	1*	2*
Lotion	0.16, 0.35, 0.40	0.98, 0.74, 0.35	0.13, 0.58, 0.40	0.64, 0.74, 0.29
Ointment	0.22, 0.15, 0.26	0.12, 0.24, 0.3	0.55, 0.25, 0.32	0.30, 0.40, 0.37
Cream	0.12, 0.35, 0.56	0.46, 0.72, 0.33	0.30, 0.43, 0.46	0.38, 0.88, 0.32

* With pyrocatechol reagent.

* With l-noradrenaline bitartrate reagent.

was followed. 10 ml of this stock solution was neutralised with 0.1 N NaOH before making it to 100 ml. The solution was again filtered before use.

Recovery experiment : To find out the reliability of the method, the procedure of standard addition was followed. To a 0.4 ml (40 mg resorcinol) sample, three different levels of the standard solution, viz., 0.4, 0.6 and 0.8 ml were added and colour development was carried out as described. From the absorbance value the total amount of drug was calculated. Each concentration level was repeated seven times. The recovery of the added drug was calculated by using the formula

$$\% \text{ recovery} = \frac{N(\Sigma XY) - (\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)}{N(\Sigma X^2) - (\Sigma X)^2}$$

where

X = amount of standard added.

Y = amount of drug found by the proposed method.

N = number of observations.

The results of recovery experiment, the standard deviation and coefficient of variation at above levels are tabulated in Tables 1 and 2.

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